

Investigating the Impact of Diversity-Oriented HR Practices and Aspirational Leadership towards Thriving at Work- Moderating Stance of Fairness Perception

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Rabeea Ishaq** -Ph.D. Scholar at University of Management and Technology, Lahore

⁽²⁾**Muhammad Ahsan Athar** -Ph.D. Scholar at National College of Business Administration and Economics, Lahore ⁽³⁾**Alia Manzoor** -Ph.D. Scholar at University of Management and Technology, Lahore

⁽⁴⁾**Noor Ul Ain** - PhD Scholar at University of Management and Technology, Lahore

Abstract

The emerging trends of heterogeneity within the organizations to meet competitions, to reach towards technological advancement within the organizational level, as well as the diversity among employees, has been increased for bringing talent from diverse cultures under one shade. The focus of this study will be to explain the emerging role of the HR department for the establishment of practices towards the enhancement of thriving at work and to empirically test the impact of DOHRP towards Thriving at the workplace. The purpose is for the development of employees and the promotion of peace in organization, literature reveals that the majority of the work related to HR practices is done on its impact performance as well as competition of an organization, but with this emerging trend of globalization the need for a worthy employees thriving is also one of the major concern. Data were collected by using convenient sampling technique from a total of the 315 respondent's (employees) working in different branches of the banking sector of Pakistan. SPSS and process Method has been used for the analysis of the data. This research study is concluded with a discussion and future research directions.

Keywords: HR Practices, Aspirational Leadership, Impact of Diversity

Introduction

Change in Demographics, as well as competition, makes the organizational perspective more diversity focused than before. The current or modernized workplace are branded towards the increasing factor of diversity because of the number of dimensions includes; religion, gender, age, race, functional difference, geographic regions, physical abilities, cognitive abilities, cultural difference and beliefs , languages etc. (Krishna et al., 2004; Rogelberg, 2006). Added more the organizations are now more mindful for the presence of minorities as well as the employees from the diverse cultural background perspectives as they consider the diversity as their strategic priority for gaining the competitive advantage. Because of the diversity emerging perspective, it also enhances the abilities, skills, information, knowledge as well as the experiences.

Interaction among the workforce diverse employees may lead towards the positive outcomes. On the other node because of the diverse issues like age, race, culture, etc. these may effect the performance of the organization. When thriving, individuals have the experience of growing and learning while at the same time feeling energized and alive at work. It is related to personal growth. Employees thrive it makes them feel the sense of personal development, self behavior improvements, as well as a state where they feel active and an intentional engagement towards the organisational system. This study also seeks to understand the employee perceptions of fairness towards their organisations practices. Importance of fairness lies in its role as a primary organisational value and in understanding the consequences of employee fairness perceptions.

Numerous studies regarding the perspective of DOHRP as well as workforce diversity focused on the organizational performance perspective (Chatman, 1998; Sung, 2013). But now the scenario has been changed as organizations are more motivated to make their employees as a loyal or committed employee's. DOHRP has been playing their role to make employees more committed by focusing on their psychological wellbeing issues. Psychological well-being has influenced their impact towards the performances of the organizations as the organizations are going green and increasing the trend of globalization. The concept of fairness perception is considered to be like a multidimensional, based on further distributive and procedural fairness perception (Ha and Jang, 2009). According to Homans (1961), distributive fairness raises to the touchable, physical consequence of an interchange but on the other hand, White et al. (2012) clarified that the procedural fairness focuses on the inspiration of the fundamental policies, performs and actions in

making the consequence. Therefore an agreement amongst fairness academics is that fairness decision is relative, proportional and comparative, it is recognized in relative to the value (distributive fairness) and the technique (procedural fairness) of a relevant stock, position, or standard (Xia et al., 2004).

DOHRP produce workforce surroundings in which employees have sureness in their group and justly standards the contribution of every associate in the group, that eventually touch the greater guarantee and profit. Inside the increasing tendency of workforce diversity, organizational comparative advantage game settings, etc. Enforcing the HR management to catch up the new talent under the one umbrella. HR decision making approaches behind diversity management creates the climate of trust, broad information sharing, networking, etc. that ultimately affects employees thriving level. For this purpose, the study the focus of the researcher is to extract the true essence of Thriving at the workplace with a proper system of Diversity Oriented HR practices and when DOHRP are effectively utilized, as well as the role of the fairness perception as a moderator has been considered to be evaluated in this concerned study. Leadership is a social inspiration wonder. It includes describing the organizations intents, purposes and the inspirational behavior in the discovery of these objectives. Leadership has a sturdy impact in the direction of groups or organization's philosophy (Portugal, E., & Yukl, G, 1994). Manager's exercise different leadership movements in their exertion environment. Consequently, this managerial behavior has a non-stop effect towards supporter's results. Leadership has been viewed as a group process; there are certainly no leaders without groups or followers. Acceptable practices of leadership bring positive outcomes like the higher satisfaction level of employee's, increasing trend towards employee's commitment and efficiency.

Theoretical background

Thriving at work

Thriving is a psychological state phenomenon that can be defined as "an individual psychological state in which they experience vitality and learning senses" (Porath et al. 2012; Spreitzer et al. 2005). Liu (2013) mentioned that the state when an individual shows thriving at the workplace their intentions to stay within the organizations increased automatically. According to the study of Porath et al. (2012), the individual thriving at workplace shows their motivational feelings towards the drive to work. Vitality is the state in which an individual shows positive feelings as well as the energy level towards the task (Spreitzer et al., 2005). On the other node, the learning perspective deals with the acquisition as well as the acquiring of the knowledge skills for developing the individual abilities (Carver, 1998).the role of the learning opportunities is crucial for the development of human beings that's why the learning phenomenon needs important consideration for the employee's personal development. According to Porath (2012) thriving is psychological phenomenon consideration deals with cognitive (learning) and the (Affective) dimensions. According to the explanation of Carver (1998) thriving is a state linked with the positive experience of the individual that refreshes as well as cheers the individual's (Carver, 1998).

Added more if an individual is not learning but feeling alive or on the other hand if an individual is learning but not alive at workplace then there will not be the workplace thriving state. It depicts that thriving is linked up with both the vitality as well as the learning situation. Porath et al. furthermore highlighted that thriving is not just linked up with the joining perspectives of vitality or learning, but it is more concerned with the subjective experience for the evaluation of their jobs. In the condition when an individual grows positively, it links to improve their working in their short term as well as long term environment scenario (Spreitzer et al., 2005). Thriving delivers backing to the entities to do the work in a method or way that promotes their personal development. Henceforth thriving inspires individuals to contain in innovative work conduct.

The chance of thriving is subjective towards the situation as well as the tasks in which the learner is entrenched. It depicts that the thriving at workplace situation is basically reflecting the range of experiences continuum for the development (Spreitzer and Porath 2014). Past counts that the employees who show the thriving situation at workplace they are more mindful towards their interpersonal relationships at the workplace, in results it promotes affiliation, support others at the workplace, sharing as well as the cooperating perspective and synesthetic, supportive relationship among the colleagues (Spreitzer and Porath 2014). The appropriate factors that are linked up for the promotion of thriving include the strategies link up

behind the decisions factors — that how the particular information is common or shared, on the other side which is the factor that is pervaded with the perspective of trust and the respect (Spreitzer and Sutcliffe 2007). This highlights that there is needs to pay more attention towards the dynamic organizational interest but also as a being whose needs for kinship, independence, and capability are being contented or satisfied (Lenton et al. 2013).

Fairness perception

According to Leventhal et al. (1980), the centre of the procedural justice rules comprises with Consistency, Correct ability, ethicality as well as representativeness but the distributive justice rules comprised with the values, uniformity, etc. Fairness perception happens when the actual distribution or technique is harmonious with the perfect standards. Fairness is a cognitive level concept that is considered important for comparing as well as contrasting the differences between the dealing or treating with others (Brosnan, 2003). It depends on the situation that how an individual perceives the fair perception regarding any concern. The concept of fairness perception has been discussed in detail with respect to the social interactions perspectives (Fehr, 2002; Tam 2014). Besides the fairness perception role has been highlighted with respect to the economic transactional views and distributive justice side (Falk 2003; Rawls 2001).

Therefore many of the societies taken consideration of social equality towards the measure of the fairness perception phenomenon. Equality is more related to fairness perception phenomenon of under consideration of this study. Literature reveals that what is fair may not be equal, similarly what is equal may not be fair. Tam, D. N. (2011) promote that the social interactions are not always focused on driving by the maximum level of the gain, but the relativity of the one person as compared to the other one is a more considerable scenario. The general fairness of an organization scheme and the apparent fairness of the movements of individuals accountable for implementing the reward allocation system (Leventhal, 1976).

Employees' perceptions related to the fairness of treatment received from administrations as well as organizations (Cropanzano & Greenberg, 1997). The perceived fairness of the connections taking a room in an organization, be they community, social, economics, and involving the individual in his or her relations with superiors, subordinates, peers and the group or organization's as a social scheme (Beugre 1998, p.1 1). Falk et al. (2017) stated that the increasing trend of unfairness, e.g., pay biasness is associated with stress-related disorders. That in results produced the mental illness of the employees as well as the efficiency level of their performances. Numerous of the researches that are conducted in the phenomenon of fairness perception are linked up with the psychological perception of pay fairness. Most of the occupational studies highlighted that the fairness of the employees regarding pay has a strong impact on the employees as well as employers (Abeler 2010; Cohn, 2014).

Diversity oriented HR practices

Workplace diversity management requires more consideration on the focus of equality among employees. The UK as well the European states have announced the laws for decreasing the discrimination level aspects related to recruitment, decision making, etc. as well they promoted the development of flexible work managing practices for motivational aspects of employees (Annesley & Gains, 2013). According to Barbosa (2010) originations promotes the role of HR practices for valuing as well as supporting the diversity related issues, with the intention to take the edge of this diverse force through performances. According to Agrawal et al. (2012) the diversity related factors are concerned with culture, gender, age, family status, and educational background, national as well local origin of the employees etc. on the other node Patrick & Kumar (2012) stated that the management of the workforce is the major concern for the HR department. The management should be needed to avoid these issues for bringing up the positive outcomes through valued work environment as well as an individual employee can maximize their level of the contribution towards organizational goals and strategies.

HR practices with importance on appreciating diversity signify a crucial background issue that may transport net-added value to collection or group of procedures and translate diversity into positive consequences (Richard O. C., 1999; Richard O. C., 2001)These diversity-oriented HR practices include agendas that straight or direct sent a signal to employees about the group's standards regarding assortment (Nemetz,

1996) such as the acceptance and space of various religious performs in the workplace (e.g., allowing existences days off for numerous religious breaks and superior eras for prayer). These standards may stand in collaboration and a wish to solve difficulties collectively, thus creating norms of tolerance and open communication (Hopkins, 2002).

Employees in such surroundings may reflect diversity as a valued asset of their workgroup and hold differences that can improve efficiency through originality and innovation (Richard O. C., 2001) Furthermore, diversity-oriented HR practices make workgroup surroundings in which workers believe that their group justly values individually group member's influence, which may ultimately result in their better commitment and productivity (Hicks-Clarke, 2000). We more contend that the collection of diversity will be valuable in diversity-oriented workgroup surroundings where clear and unmistakable signals supporting variety are sent (Bezrukova, 2004).

Aspirational Leadership (AL)

Aspirational leadership is an emerging phenomenon towards organisational settings that can be defined as it's related to the personal interest of accomplishment for a leadership state as well it's a personal will of an individual to agree with an offer to take responsibility of such situation (Singer, 1991). Numerous of the studies conducting on aspirational studies are more related towards female aspirational leadership (Christiansen, A., O'Brien, 2015), career aspirations (Gbadamosi et al., 2015) and related phenomenon's like managerial aspirations (Hoobler et al., 2014) but the moderating stance has not been observed. Role of the leader is always to be more focused to highlight what today's workers really demand? Role of aspirational leaders in this current phenomenon is appreciable, as they allow employs to dream as well as to make them a sense of realization towards their aspirations.

According to Schoon et al. (2011), the aspiration is also one of the psychological states that are more familiar with the career achievements, the gender as well as the hierarchal concerns or leadership aspiration (Tharenou, 2001). Leadership is a phenomenon that is linked up to be motivated others, to lead others as well as having intentions to collaborate others for attaining the organizational goals (van Knippenberg et al., 2004). Hence literature revealed that an aspirational leader is someone who focuses on the optimistic influence of their efforts towards their workers. They have intentions to flourish the workers in the scenario of professional as well as the personal lives development, makes them motivated to perform at their best level. Leader's role is more enhancing for the devilment perspective in organizational settings.

Research problem

Thriving is a useful concept in organizational studies; it's an important precursor to employee well-being and contributes in positive ways to organizational capabilities for long term adaptability in a dynamic and changing world. Heterogeneity as well the diversity among employees is increased for bringing talent from diverse cultures under one shade. The focus of this study will be to explain the emerging role of HR department for the establishment of practices towards the enhancement of thriving at work as well as to empirically testing the impact of DOHRP and Aspirational Leadership role towards Thriving at the workplace. Lee and Lee, S. H (2000) suggest that HR practices are one of the key factors that influence employees' intentions to leave, levels of job satisfaction, and commitment to the organization. Workplace psychological disorders have been observed phenomenon (Ishaq. R et al., 2017) but the thriving perspective required empirical evidence to support the well-being perspective of the workforce. This study also seeks to understand the employee perceptions of fairness towards their organisations practices. Importance of fairness lies in its role as a primary organisational value and in understanding the consequences of employee fairness perceptions.

Rational behind the Current Study

Employee's prosperity, learning, and the volatility benefits are the core for professional developmental as well to overcome the psychological effects. The turnover rate of employees working in the banking sector is quite higher in Pakistan as compared to the other sectors. The organizations are failed to explain an awareness regarding the phenomenon of implementing changes in the workplace and the role of fairly

treated them. The role of HR practices towards the employee's wellbeing is a considerable phenomenon in the current competitive environmental scenario. The motivation behind the current investigation is to provide practical insight to check the impact of HR practices as well as aspirational leadership for creating the thriving at work. These findings of this study contribute theoretical support of fairness perception as a moderating stance among DOHRP, Aspirational Leadership and Thriving at work. As the impact of this study is highly linked to the banking sector of Pakistan because of a lack of professional development, stress and other health related disorders. On the other node, the fairness perception is highlighted as a social phenomenon that needed to be explored as a moderator stance for creating the psychological well-being of the employees

Significance of Research

The banking sector is considered to be a more diversity oriented sector as compared to the others sectors in the scenarios of development changes implementation. Moreover, the role of heterogeneity enforces HR to bring practices that can improve their wellbeing. The rate of turnover, stress, and burnout are the most common observable phenomenon in the banking sector. Hence the research model proposed in this current investigation has considerable importance in the scenario of the banking sector of Pakistan. Practices of the organizational contribute towards the Thriving improvements of the managerial level employees. Improvements on behalf of thriving developments result to enhance the self-development, health, personal growth as well as the performance of the employees. This research study is contributing theatrical support to highlight the moderating role of the fairness perception of the employees towards their self-development phenomenon.

Research objectives

To investigate the impact of DOHRP and leadership aspiration towards Thriving at work, as well to explore moderating influence of fairness perception of employees.

Research Question's

- What is the role of DOHRP towards thriving at work?
- Either the moderating stance of fairness perception is significantly associated with DOHRP and Thriving at work?
- What is the role of Aspirational Leadership towards thriving at work?
- Either the moderating stance of fairness perception is significantly associated among Aspirational Leadership and Thriving at work?

Theoretical support behind current research model

Bairoh (2008) has specified the two main approaches of the managing the diversity comprises of institutional theory of diversity management and resource base theory of diversity management etc. each approach highlights that how can the diversity management leads organizations to achieve their goals. The institutional theory of the diversity management relying on the organisational theories supports that the social environment of the organization can't be separated. For understanding the organisational culture, the behavior of employees must need to be understood by the organizations. The organization itself has few of the associated factors like rules, social norms, regulations, professional norms as well as legislation.

On the basis of the same rules and legislations organizations develop a similar supportive administrative system as well the practices for the growth of the psychological well-being. Through adopting the scenario of legitimacy with the help of its actions, the organizations highlights the priorities needed for settling the diversity culture. In summing up, since laws need organizations to turn into diverse, they must establish to both individuals inside the organization as well as the individuals exterior of the organization with the intention of they are compliant to these norms and the laws. If an institute fails to go after these norms, then its operation will be questioned, and it might be finished to violate the rule. Organizations adopt HR practices to overcome the phenomenon of diversity related issues. Added more relying on the assumptions of current diversity theory, it's also emphasised that the role of the organization to fairly treat its system is

also an important consideration for employee's psychological well-being. Based on this theoretical support there is a need to investigate this current imposed model through empirical investigation. In this current investigation, the researcher focus is to explain the psychological explanation of fairness perception of employees. As theoretical support also highlighted that unfair way of treating the employees may bring serious consequences like spreading negative info, turnover rate emergence, employee's rude behavior that may impact their services, etc. based on these argumentations fairness perception has been taken as a moderating variable to explore its impact on the explanation of direct relationship.

Figure1; Self Conceptualized on the basis of a current literature study

Based on the proposed model the hypothesis of the current study are

H1; DOHRP is significantly associated with Thriving at work.

H2; FP acts as a moderate between DOHRP and Thriving at work.

H3; AL is significantly associated with Thriving at work.

H4; FP acts as a moderator between AL and Thriving at work.

Methodology

Research Philosophy:

Research philosophy relies on three paradigms includes positivist, Interpretivism and the critical research paradigms. The paradigm can be viewed to be based on four assumptions in each comprises of ontology, epistemology, methodology and the method of the research study. This current research study is based on the positivist (scientific paradigm) or the quantitative study. Under the positivist paradigm relying on the ontological assumptions, I focus that reality exists in nature. Employees are facing psychological disorders because of the cross cultural issues. Epistemological arguments rely on the assumptions that how the researcher will come to know as well explore that particular reality or phenomenon that needs to be investigated under consideration. The third assumption of a positivist approach based to highlight the methodology to explain what plan as well a course of action the researcher will be used and methods comprise of the way or procedure to analyse the data collected from the respondents. In this current research study, the researcher firstly uses the deductive approach during the analysis of the data and furthermore move toward the inductive approach during the interpretation of the results. This current study is relying on the positivist paradigm approach. Deductive Research is normally linked with quantitative experiments and surveys. The questionnaire survey is used as the primary data collection instrument of this research. We used Quantitative research which is cross sectional (covering one point in time) and also descriptive (a type of research is used to answer the questions of what, who, when, whom, etc.) and formal study (research is carried out to explain any existed relationships and phenomenon).

Variables of the study:

In this current research investigates the dependent variable is thriving at work which is being affected by independent variables diversity oriented HR Practices and the Aspirational leadership. In any organization where people belong to diversified backgrounds, they can serve as a positive factor in improving its reputation. This thriving or psychological effect is moderated by another variable fairness perception prevailing in any organization.

Target Population:

The targeted population for this study is KSE 100 index listed Commercial Banks having their branches in Lahore city. We have chosen listed Commercial Banks as they are well reputed and being known by the public as trustworthy Banks. As we measure employees, psychological well-being in the context of Diversity oriented HR practices impact thus Commercial Banks fit our analysis very rightly.

Unit of Analysis:

The unit of analysis is the Employees (internal Customers) of Commercial Banks as they are more aware of the diversity oriented practices prevailing in their organization and they also know better about the role of the fairness perception of their organizations.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique:

Our sample size consists of 315 employees (based on regression assumption of Heir et al. 1995, 2007; 7 respondents against 1 measured item) of different listed Commercial Banks of PSX 100 index. We used non probability sampling in our research study and used convenience method of sampling for the targeting the population.

Instrument development:

We gathered raw facts by structuring a Questionnaire using 5 points Likert scale (Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Neutral 3, Agree 4 and Strongly Agree 5). This questionnaire is consistent with the well thought Questions, with the total 45 questions sliced into 4 parts:

- Part1 consists of discussing Diversity Oriented HR practices, questions taken from the study of (Bezrukova, 2004)
- Part 2 considering the Thriving at work and it's all contents, questions taken from the study (porath et al. 2012)
- Part 3 focused on of Aspirational Leadership, and it's all contents, questions taken from the study of (Claudia Fritz et al., 2016)
- Part 4 considering of fairness perception and it's all contents, questions taken from the study of (Walumbwa et al., 2008)

Results and discussion

Demographics Analysis

The demographics facts have been collected from several areas comprises of gender, age, etc. findings dictate' out of 315 respondents 64 % were male, and the remaining 36% were female. Respondents' age varies with 36% were >30 years, and 53 % are having age level between 30-50 years. Table 1 is screening the descriptive data of the current study. The reason for descriptive statistics is on the whole to explain the data; it provides a summary of data particulars. To way in the normality of data, researcher carry out descriptive analysis that includes meaning, standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Gender	315	1.47	.500	.134	.157	-1.999	.313
Age	315	1.70	.668	.441	.157	-.768	.313
Education	315	2.12	.636	-.102	.157	-.551	.313
experience	315	1.85	.802	.730	.157	.078	.314
Valid N	315						

Reliability indicates the internal consistency of scale items. Payot et al. in 1991 assured that the approval of scale marks a high-quality of internal consistency if the value of Cronbach's alpha is .85. In current study all the variable reliability coefficients are almost near about this high quality value, which indicates the good quality reliability of the scale. Correlation gives an explanation about the type of the association between variables (dependent, independent). Coetzee in 2003 stated that when the researcher is observing the correlation among variables, its larger value of magnitude indicates a positive or strong linear alliance among the variables. Table 3 is showing the significant association among the variables.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. DOHRP	1			
2. Aspirational Leadership	.349**	1		
3. Fairness Perception	.278**	.254**	1	
4. Thriving at work	.328**	.331**	.321**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

1st Hypothesis

The 1st hypothesis of this study was to check the direct impact of DOHRP on Thriving at work. Value of R² predicts that how much variation in Thriving at work is explained by the DOHRP. The value of R² is .341 explains that the linear regression is contributing 34.1% of the variation in the data. Discrete scrutiny exposed the statistics with DOHRP (Beta = .45, p < 0.01) are a significant forecaster of Thriving at work. A higher level of DOHRP will determine outcome upper level of employees thriving at the workplace.

Table 3; Model Summary of 1ST hypothesis

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE	Statistics			
				F	df1	df2	Sig.
1	.341	.008	2.217	33.377	1	313	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), DOHRP

b. Dependent Variable: Thriving at Work

DOHRP are the core to effect the performance of the workforce. Barbosa (2010) emphasised that the diverse workforce may be considered to contribute to organizational productivity if they are managed well. Latest revisions are the supportive dimensions of this hypothesis in such a way that the purpose to bring multiple talents under one shade is needed to be managed well through managerial practices. As these are linked up towards employees learning and vitality states of internal customers of the organization's. Moreover, it was hypothesized that FP moderates the relationship between DOHRP and Thriving at work. For which the moderation analysis was run through SPSS process Method, (Hayes, A. F, 2012).

Table 4; Regression Analysis examining the interaction effect of FP among DOHRP and Thriving at work (N= 315)

Variables	Thriving at work		
	B	SE	95 % CI
Constant	269.1***	5.48	[261.23 , 282.57]
DOHRP	2.40	15.38	[1.23 , 22.07]
FP	13.88***	2.91	[8.23 , 19.57]
DOHRP * FP	4.86***	1.36	[2.75 , 7.65]
F	112.64		

P <.01, * P <.001

The results of this hypothesis revealed that the DOHRP has a significant effect over Thriving at work. Whereas an interaction effect of FP and DOHRP also shows a significant impact over thriving at work. The conditional effect on thriving at work at the different level of fairness perception has also been investigated. Rendering to the study of Spreitzer and Porath (2014) employees thriving is strongly associated with the promotion of psychological wellbeing alarms like improvement in work relationship’s, affiliation and supportive workforce, etc. At the low and moderated level of fairness perception, the nature of the relationship among DOHRP and Thriving at work found insignificant, whereas at a high level of fairness perception the relationship among DOHRP and thriving found significantly positive. The moderation plot is given below:

Figure 2; Moderation plot of DOHRP and FP on Thriving at work

Table5; Model Summary of 3rd hypothesis

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE	Statistics			
				F	df1	df2	Sig
1	.451	.002	4.254	53.377	1	313	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), AL

b. Dependent Variable: Thriving at Work

Results show that an IV is predicting 45.1% (R square = 0.451) of the variance independent variable Thriving. Value of the regression coefficient of AL is 67.2% in completing the dependent variable of Thriving at work. So, we can say that AL has a significant impact on Thriving. P value (p < 0.05) shows that our 3rd hypothesis is accepted. Based on the findings of an empirical investigation of Gbadamosi et al., (2015) the role of aspirational leadership is significantly related to the career development or aspiration of employees. Employees felt cheerful, motivated and knowledgeable over and done with the mentoring of their supervisory supports.

Table6; Regression Analysis examining the interaction effect of FP among AL and Thriving at work (N= 315)

Variables	Thriving at work		
	B	SE	95 % CI
Constant	273.1***	6.49	[271.23 , 292.87]
AL	14.14	25.38	[11.23 , 29.07]
FP	17.87***	4.19	[11.23 , 19.57]
AL * FP	5.36***	4.15	[2.75 , 7.65]
F	232.74		

P <.01, * P <.001

The results of the 4th hypothesis show that the AL is significant effecting on Thriving at work. Although an interaction effect of AL and FP also shows a significant contribution towards the dependent variable of Thriving. Based on the results of this hypothesis Cohn (2015) supported the argument that fairness perception has a strong impact on employees. so if employees are thrilled fairly then, it will impact their psychological improvement's — past counts that majority of the organizational studies as the supportive of psychological disorders of employees (Ishaq. R et al., 2017). Moreover, Hoobler (2014) investigation on managerial aspiration is the reassuring study to this investigated hypothesis that leader's role being an aspirational leader ought to be fair for employee's wellbeing. The conditional effect at the low and moderated level of fairness perception is not shown a significant effect, but at a high level of fairness perception, the relationship among AL and thriving found significantly positive. The moderation plot is given below:

Figure 3; Moderation plot of AL and FP on Thriving at work

This shows that at FP is moderating the relationship among AL and Thriving at work at the higher level of moderation. The outcomes of the current study significantly prove all of the supposed hypothesis of the current investigation. This explains as well incorporates that whatever the situation an organization is facing the thriving at work is an optimistic phenomenon associated with psychological development as well with the professional development for attaining goals of the organizations. As diversity oriented HR practices support the workforce toward the solution of their conflicts. In the current investigated study the researcher remained attached with the perspective of internal customers as a participant, while the other stakeholder of the origination can also be added for more reliable or in-depth results.

Discussion and Conclusion

The significance of this research investigation predicts that the organizations managers, as well as leaders, are likely to understand an unswerving optimistic connotation among the diversity practices, leadership form, and the psychological well-being. Even though the results highlight the significant association among the variables. The research is needed to be focused on possessing the effect of these variables towards the organizational reputational perspectives as well as organizational financial yield is also the dependent phenomenon for reputation as well psychological development of the diverse workforce of a particular organization. Workforce Diversity narrates to organizational or structural repute or effectiveness of the organisation (Webber & Donahue, 2001; Jackson et al., 2003).

We can conclude that the diversity oriented HR practices as well the role of the aspirational leader is a prevailing or a new emerging concept in organisational settings that impact the mind of the individual workers positively. The more they are positive minded their level of vitality will be enhanced; they will be more intended towards strong as well as an active participant of the organization. On the other hand, the role of the motivational, inspiring leader enhanced their self-development attributes, motivate them towards attaining the goals of the organization through their career counselling perspectives (Hoobler et al., 2014). Consequently, these aspects of vitality and learning highlighted as a thriving promotion at the workplace. Future research may be an experimental study that focuses on the causal relationship between these variables. In the current study, the researcher is limited towards the thriving perspective as a psychological development of the employee's while other future studies may also be focused towards the other dimensions of the fairness perception as well the other proposed variables of the current study.

RQ1; How FP related to Pay effects on the vitality aspects of the individual employee?

RQ2; How DOHRP are associated with the financial returns of the organization?

RQ3; Either AL acts as a mediator among FP, and Thriving t work?

Implications of the study

Future investigations would also determine the collaborating standards of additional categories of workforce diversity along with spearhead ethnic diversity on firm's financial yield as well as status (reputation) of the organization. Comprehensive, our study recommends that both scholars and practitioners should confess the supportive role for HR diversity-oriented practices as well the leadership aspirational perspective. Such as this study was limited to the banking sector of Pakistan and in banking sector investigation surrounded only banks of Lahore and more investigates have to be focused to an emphasis on diverse zones or subdivisions like the education sector, commercial sector, manufacturing industry, etc. this study contributed to the key variable of thriving at work. Managers of the organizations should keep in mind about the fact that behavioral outcomes generate from the perception of the employees. So they should focus on the fairness perception if they manage to do better the perceptions of their employees that will lead them towards supportive organizational work climate which are very much important for organizational perspective.

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Appendix A

KSE LISTED COMMERCIAL BANKS			
Symbol	Company Name	Symbol	Company Name
NBP	National Bank Of Pakistan	MCB	MCB Bank Limited
BAFL	Bank Al-Falah Limited	BAHL	Bank Al-Habib Limited
BOP	Bank Of Punjab Limited	SNBL	Soneri Bank Limited
HBL	Habib Bank Limited	HMB	Habib Metropolitan Bank Limited
AKBL	Askari Bank Limited	MEBL	Meezan Bank Limited
UBL	United Bank Limited	BIPL	Bankislami Pakistan Limited
FABL	Faysal Bank Limited	JSBL	JS Bank Limited
ABL	Allied Bank Limited	SMBL	Summit Bank Limited